

THE STRUCTURE AND COMPOSITION OF THE MINING INDUSTRY IN THE OHANGARON VALLEY.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6524567>

Shadiyeva Khilola Dilmurod qizi

Tashkent State Pedagogical University

1st year student of master's degree

Abstract: *This article is about the the structure and composition of the mining industry in the Ohangaron valley. Furthermore, resent facts and goal in mining industry were given.*

Key Words: *Mining industry, less-diverse, solid, small-scale industry, licence, subsoil-use, source-level, strategic industries.*

Mining industry is one of the most prominent earning source of many different countries, since the growth of the mining industries often regulate the resource acquisition potential and economic growth of the countries. Based on different characteristics of the mining industries, this industry might be categorized under geophysical industries or chemical industries. However, though mining industry is a very less-diverse and small industrial setting, understanding the waste management initiatives or exploring initiatives in order to minimize mining-generated waste at source level, are necessary to tackle any accidents or to protect the surround environment and environmental components. Mining industry indicates the cluster of process that are involved with extraction, management, and processing of naturally occurring solid minerals from the earth surface. As a product of mining, various economically valuable products might be obtained, that is, coal, diamond, metallic ores, oil, and so on.

Mining industry also involve processes associated with mineral processing, surface mining, market of mining equipment, etc. Sustainability of the mining industries is largely correlated with its corresponding industrial impacts on the environment, since there are enough evidences of the detrimental impacts of mining industry on environment. Despite the negative impacts that mining industry may bring about, there is no scope to bypass the positive outcome that this industry assures. Despite being a very small-scale industry with quite less interaction with other industries, it is noted that in 2019, the global mining equipment market size has been found to be 1,21,694.3 million USD that is predicted to be at least 1,65,827.8 million USD by 2027 with a potential compound annual growth rate (CAGR)

of 5.7% (ReportLinker, 2020). Looking at the potential market size of mining industry, the impact of mining industry in the world economy is easily understandable. Many of the mined goods are used for energy production and used as raw materials for chemical industries which also let the mining industry control the growth of other industries such as energy production industry, chemical industry, electrical industry, electronics industry, and so on.

Uzbekistan's mining industry is one of the country's most important and strategic industries. Uzbekistan is one of the world's largest producers of gold (ranked ninth) and of uranium (ranked seventh). Uzbekistan also produces copper, silver, coal, phosphate, molybdenum, potassium, tungsten, lead, zinc and other minerals. Uzbekistan possesses most types of minerals. Different regions focus on different minerals. For example, Navoi province is famous for its large deposits of gold and uranium and Tashkent province for copper, coal and gold deposits. The most active regions are Navoi, Samarkand and Tashkent provinces. Uzbekistan's legal system is based on civil law, which is similar to the Romano–Germanic system of law. Exploration and development of minerals is regulated under a number of national laws and regulations. Exploration and mining rights are granted on the basis of a subsoil-use licence awarded to the subsoil user, through tenders or direct negotiations, by the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Geology and Mineral Resources.

The main act regulating the mining industry is the Law on Subsoil No. 444-II, new edition, dated 13 December 2002 (Subsoil Law). The Subsoil Law provides the fundamental legal framework governing exploration and development of all subsoil resources, including both minerals and oil and gas. The Subsoil Law provides for state licensing and control, rights and obligations, basic rules regarding efficient use of resources, types of subsoil use, duration of subsoil use, and other matters. The industry is also regulated under a number of other laws and regulations, including the Resolution of the President of Uzbekistan on Terms and Conditions on Granting of Subsoil Use Rights No. PP-649 dated 7 June 2007 (Regulation PP-649), the Tax Code, Land Code, Labour Code and Environment Protection Law. It shall be noted that Regulation PP-649 established a procedure for granting a licence on subsoil-use rights for all subsoil minerals excluding construction materials. Granting subsoil-use rights for exploration and development of deposits of construction materials is regulated by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Terms and Conditions on Granting of Subsoil Use Rights for Deposits of Construction Materials No. PP-

1524 dated 2 May 2011. In addition to the above, the Law on Concessions dated 30 August 1995 (Concession Law) provides a legal basis for this form of right to develop mineral resources. However, this law has not yet been widely applied in practice. To date, there have not been any examples of concessions being negotiated and entered for mining projects in Uzbekistan. The difference between the regulatory framework in Uzbekistan and that of other countries is in the absence of any separation between mining and petroleum law and a common approach towards regulation of the mining industry and the oil and gas industry.

The confusion is exacerbated by the Law on Production Sharing Agreements dated 7 January 2001 (PSA Law). The PSA Law applies, in addition to the Subsoil Law, in the case of affairs related to the conclusion, execution and termination of PSAs in the exploration and mining of mineral resources in Uzbekistan. The principal regulatory bodies that administer the laws and regulations related to mining are the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Geology and Mineral Resources (Geology Committee), the State Inspectorate of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Control over Industrial Safety of works in Industry, Mining, Geology and Public Utilities Sectors (Industrial Safety Inspectorate) and the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Protection of the Environment (Environment Protection Committee). However, mining industry is a very old industry due to the age-old anthropogenic dependency of the human being on the natural resources. Since the Stone Age, mining industry has developed and gradually adopted today's shape of the mining industry.

The potentials and capacity of mining also help a country to control the growth of their economy. For instance, countries of the Middle East, have been successful to extract oil and thus, they have achieved tremendous economic growth over the years. Only existence of geological resources is not enough to assure economic growth, if innovative and modern inclusions are not assured alongside the contemporary processes of mining. For example, with the aid of the government of China, the country could promote their mining industry; especially coal extraction, utilizing many innovative ideas (Fan et al., 2017). However, there are many challenges associated with this mining industry that includes, lack of sustainable approaches, need for expensive and advanced technologies, geo-physical or climatic variables, and so on. Besides, the huge amount of waste produced from this industry is also another big challenge to be tackled in this sector. In 2010, the Almalyk mining and metallurgical complex (Almalyk GMK) was the only copper production company in

Uzbekistan. The mining of copper in Uzbekistan takes place in the Sary-Cheku and Kalmakyr deposits. Besides mining of copper, the Almalyk GMK is also involved in the mining and processing of lead-zinc-barite ores obtained from the Uch-Kulach deposit in Jizzax Viloyati. In 2010, about 20% of gold and 90% of silver was produced by Uzbekistan's Almalyk GMK.

To conclude all facts above, we should stressed that the huge amount of waste produced from such a leading industry, mining industry, this chapter aims to explore the major types of waste produced from mining industries and at the same time, this chapter also suggests suitable approaches to be adopted in order to assure source-level minimization of mining industry-produced waste.

REFERENCES:

1. Chaudhery Mustansar Hussain, .Samiha Nuzhat, in Source Reduction and Waste Minimization, 2022
2. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/mining-industry>
3. <http://minerals.usgs.gov/minerals/pubs/country/2010/myb3-2010-uz.pdf>
4. The State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Geology and Mineral Resources, <https://uzgeolcom.uz/en/page/78>